

ON THE BROMINATION OF CRESOL

By N. RAY

A process of inhibiting the overbromination of the cresols has been worked out, which is found to be independent of temperature as well as of the concentration of bromine or acid added. A mechanism of the overbromination and of its inhibition has been explained. An easy and accurate method of estimating cresols by bromination has also been suggested.

Cresol is a mixture of its three isomers which are present roughly in the proportion $o : m : p = 35 : 40 : 25$ (Chapin, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 47, 309). Of these the *m*-cresol (Beukema-Goudsmit, *Pharm. Weekblad*, 1934, 71, 380) can easily be estimated by the koppeschaar's method of bromination (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1876, 15, 233). Auwers and Anselmino (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3587) showed that liquid bromine may cause substitution in the *o*- and *p*-methyl group or even lead to the complete replacement of the *p*-methyl group. Phenol-cresol mixture and lysol (Järvinen, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 108; N. Ray, unpublished data) have been estimated to a considerable degree of accuracy assuming a more or less arbitrary value of cresol. No general procedure, however, for estimating cresol by this method is known upto now. Ruderman (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 753) found that a number of factors, such as period of bromination, the acid concentration and the temperature, influenced the potential reactivity of phenols, which may lead to overbromination under certain conditions. The effect of concentration of reactants, however, does not appear to have been investigated so far. In view of the observation (Ray, *Proc. J. Inst. Chem.*, 1944, 16, 76) that sulphanilamide is liable to be overbrominated in dilute solutions but undergoes quantitative bromination in the nucleus only in a solution saturated with an alkali halide, it appears that the overbromination of cresol in dilute solutions may also be a similar phenomenon. A study of the effect of concentration of the reactants on the bromination of cresol is of interest, and the results of the work carried so far are presented in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

One mole of cresol would theoretically require 4.8 moles of bromine for bromination in the nucleus. Thus 1 c.c. of 0.1 *N*- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ solution would be equivalent to 0.00225 g. of cresol. Relatively dilute solutions of the reactants were taken for the study of the degree of overbromination at the room temperature of 30°-33°. But in order to show the effect of high concentration of the reactants on the course of bromination either concentrations of the reactants were so adjusted that the solvent was completely or nearly saturated, or the solvent (water) of the reactants in a dilute solution was saturated by the addition of a suitable alkali halide before adding to the reactants the acid for evolution of bromine.

Method.—An aqueous solution of cresol (2 c.c.) containing 6-15 mg. was reacted with bromine from a mixture of potassium bromide and bromate solution to which 10 c.c. of 1:1 hydrochloric acid were added. This reaction was allowed for 10 minutes. The reac-

tion with potassium iodide for liberation of iodine to be titrated against $N/10$ -sodium thiosulphate was also allowed 10 minutes. The reactions were all carried out in the dark.

For dilute solution of the reactants 3 c.c. of 25% potassium bromide and 10 c.c. of 0.1*N*-potassium bromate solution were accurately measured by a pipette, and the total volume of the mixture was maintained at about 50 c.c. by the addition of water, if necessary.

TABLE I

Overbromination of cresol in dilute solutions.

Cresol taken.	B r o m i n e				Cresol found.	Over- bromination.
	Added	Consumed.	Theoretically required.	Bromine equiv. corresponding to the potential reactivity of cresol.		
6.012 mg.	80 mg.	24.39 mg.	21.38 mg.	5.477	6.86 mg.	14.1%
6.012	80	24.61	21.38	5.525	6.92	15.1
6.274	80	26.07	22.31	5.698	7.33	16.9
6.274	80	27.92	22.31	6.006	7.85	25.1
5.274	80	26.68	22.31	5.900	7.54	19.6
6.274	80	27.09	22.31	5.828	7.62	21.1
9.412	80	41.74	34.35	5.985	11.74	24.7
12.548	80	49.87	44.61	5.349	14.02	11.8
15.685	80	59.94	55.77	5.158	16.86	7.8

D I S C U S S I O N

It was found for a cresol solution containing 6.0 mg. of cresol in 50 c.c., 4 times the theoretical quantity (22.0 mg.) of bromine, under the condition of the experiment, would overbrominate the cresol to an extent which gave (Table I) 14 to 25% too high value for the cresol. When the quantity of cresol was increased, while keeping other reactants and the volume of the mixture the same, that is, with the decrease of the ratio of the amount of added bromine to that consumed, the degree of overbromination also showed a decrease, pointing to the observation of Francis and Hill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 357) that with a very slight excess of bromine the overbromination might be avoided. Table I will show that 1.43 times the required bromine *i.e.*, an excess of 24 mg. of bromine over that theoretically required gave a cresol value which was only 7.8% too high. Remembering that the nuclear substitutions have the velocity constant (Francis, Hill and Johnston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2213, 2228) of the order of 10^6 , in which case no interval is necessary for bromination after the appearance of free bromine, it might be assumed here that some bromine went over to the methyl group (Sprung, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 35) or to the

methylene quinone (cf. Ruderman, *loc. cit.*) that might have been formed, where a period of 10 minutes was given for the bromination.

On the other hand, when the volume of the solution containing the cresol was so adjusted that the added reactants, potassium bromide and bromate, completely or nearly saturated the solution, the bromination was found to be quantitative (Table II) for the nuclear substitution according to the theory.

TABLE II

Inhibition of overbromination.

Cresol taken.	KBr taken.	KBrO ₃ taken.	HCl taken.	Bromine from the bromide-bromate mixture.	Vol. of the reactant mixture.	Saturation with.	Cresol found.	Error.
9.412 mg.	750 mg.	27.83 mg.	10 c.c.	80 mg.	25 c.c.	—	9.426 mg.	+0.15%
6.274	750	27.83	10	80	20	—	6.322	+0.77
9.412	750	56.0	10	160.9	16	KCl-KBr	9.306	-1.10
9.412	2000	56.0	5	160.9	8	KBr	9.068	-3.70
9.412	750	27.83	10	80	25	NaCl	9.128	-3.02

The saturation of the dilute solution by addition of sodium chloride before adding the hydrochloric acid to the mixture of the reactants was also found to facilitate nuclear bromination only. The above observation points to the influence of solvent (water) on the extranuclear bromination of cresol. The presence of more water than is necessary for saturation (Table I) leads to substitution in the methyl group.

Alkali salts are known to be highly solvated in aqueous solution. Their presence in a high concentration would remove much of the free water and would thereby depress the solubility of bromine. Further, the increased ionic concentration in the solution would diminish the activity coefficient of bromine (Hammett, "Physical Organic Chemistry", New York, 1940, p. 90). Both these effects would tend to decrease the velocity of reaction between bromine and cresol molecules, both in the nucleus and in the side-chain. But as the velocity constant for the nuclear bromination is very high compared to that in the side-chain (Francis, Hill and Johnston, *loc. cit.*), it may be suggested that due to the presence of salts, the reaction rates are reduced to such an extent that only the faster reaction becomes effective and the slower one does not proceed to any appreciable extent during the time allowed for the reaction to proceed. It is assumed that in the absence of the salt the nuclear substitution becomes practically instantaneous and that in the side-chain is also sufficiently fast to be appreciable within the given time.

The extranuclear bromination of cresols may be considered in the light of the theory of resonance also. In the bromination of cresols it may be supposed that the directing influence of the hydroxyl group due to resonance would predominate over the inductive effect of the methyl group, and nuclear substitution would take place in the *o*- and *p*-positions to the -OH group. This would also hinder any tendency of

substitution of bromine in position *meta* to the -OH group (cf. Sprung, *loc. cit.*). While the resonance in the *m*-cresol is completely stopped by the nuclear bromination, it is not so in the case of *o*- and *p*-cresols. The resonance effect (Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 94; 1935, 57, 2705; 1937, 59, 1223) may be considered to result in the substitution of bromine in the methyl group, presumably through the formation of ionic intermediates, where the methyl carbon would be linked to the nuclear carbon through a double bond. Such a reaction would be facilitated in a hydroxylic solvent (cf. Buckles, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1157), and thus will explain the effect of high concentration of alkali salts such as bromide or chloride which removes much of the available solvent and is found to inhibit this type of reaction (Terry and Eichelberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 1067).

It will thus be evident from Table II that even a great excess of bromine could not induce bromination at the side-chain, the reaction being in presence of a high concentration of alkali halides. The temperature of the reactions of bromination was 30°-33° which might well be considered appreciably high (cf. Ruderman, Sprung, *loc. cit.*). The bromide-bromate mixture, the acid concentration, the period of reaction and the total volume of the reactant mixture were varied widely, but due to the saturation of the solvent, the bromination became quantitatively nuclear. Further evidence is necessary for elucidating the actual mechanism of the bromination.

The process of bromination of cresol in an acid solution, saturated with the alkali salt of the same acid, such as hydrochloric acid, would provide for a quick and easy method of estimating the cresols accurately with reproducible results.

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